

An investigation into the difference in the strenght and endurance of the pelvic floor muscles among women that run those that are sedentary: a cross-sectional study

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Abstract—Background: As is already widely understood, physical activity is very important to human health, however, the effects of physical activity on the pelvic floor muscles are still relatively unexplored, principally when dealing with high impact physical activity. In particular, when dealing with feminine athletes, as it is important to analyze the effects running has on the pelvic floor muscles, as this is a very popular physical activity. The objective behind this study was to compare strength and endurance of the pelvic floor muscles (PFM) among women that ran and those that were sedentary. **Methods:** The study was performed with 51 women, divided into two groups: 27 runners composed of women that run at minimum 10 km/week; and 24 sedentary women (non-runners). In order to compare the pelvic floor muscles between the two groups, evaluations for strength and endurance were used by means of digital palpation (using the Modified Oxford Scale) and vaginal cones, respectively. Strength and endurance were analyzed by means of the Mann-Whitney test. **Results:** Through the comparison of runners and sedentary individuals, one notes that women runners possess the higher scores for strength of the PFM, when compared to sedentary women ($p < 0.001$), but there is no significant difference in the endurance of the PFM during the proposed tasks. **Conclusion:** The conclusion is thus drawn

that there is a difference concerning strength in the PFM among women runners and sedentary women

Keywords — *Muscle strength, running, pelvic diaphragm, women.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The participation in some kind of sport is highly incentivized due to its inherent benefits, where running is one of the most popular physical activities. However, depending upon the intensity, this can be considered a risk toward the development of dysfunctions in the pelvic floor muscles (PFM), which can lead to Urinary Incontinence (UI) [1-2]. The continence function depends on the balance between intra-abdominal and urethral pressures, dependent on, but not only, the PFM. The stiffness of the support layer under the bladder neck functions as a barrier in which abdominal pressure compresses the urethra. The Active contraction of the urethral sphincter keeps urine in bladder while at rest. During the increase in abdominal pressure, the bladder neck and the urethral are compressed to a closed position, thus preventing the leaking of urine. The aspects of the function of the pelvic floor that are relevant to UI are associated with urethral occlusion pressures while at rest, due to the increased abdominal pressure and the recruitment of the striated urethral sphincter muscle [3].

The PFM are formed at their deepest level by the muscles of the pelvic diaphragm (pubococcygeus, puborectalis and iliococcygeus), the upper most portion of the PFM is formed by the urogenital diaphragm (ischiocavernosus, bulbospongiosus and the superficial

transverse perineal muscle). In addition to the pelvic diaphragm and the urogenital diaphragm, the external anal and urethral sphincter also make up part of the PFM muscles [1]. The PFM constitute the pelvic cavity and help to maintain consistency, thus actively supporting the pelvic organs, while closing the pelvic opening with its contracting action [4].

The PFM, through constant physical activity, should provide dynamic support, which constantly adjust their tension in response to variations in pressure, and should reflexively contract in situations of sudden increase in intra-abdominal pressure [4]. The strength in the abdominal structure of women that practice physical activity tends to be high; this can be attributed to the modality of the sport that demands abdominal muscles, as well as to the general physical training to which they are submitted. These muscles exert high levels of pressure on the PFM, in those cases where the pelvic floor muscles delay in their response to sudden changes in abdominal pressure, urinary leakage may occur [5]. It is possible that this increase in intra-abdominal pressure by training may cause functional and anatomical adaptations in athlete women [4].

The importance of studying the PFM in women runners comes from the fact that physical activity is of vital importance to individual health, as well as the population as a whole. However, many women reduce their practicing of sporting activities due to UI [6]. Studies indicate that women who participate in high impact sporting activities, as is the case of running over the long-term, due to requirement for a high volume of small forward jumps, go on to suffer higher rates of UI [7-8]. This high rate of UI may be related to the effects suffered by the PFM, due to the practicing of physical activity.

In spite of the lack of knowledge into the role of the PFM in elite athletes, some studies have found a significantly higher value in the contraction pressure of PFM in nulliparous athletes practicing high-performance sports, when compared to the group of sedentary women [6]. This, in addition to the increase in pressure of the puborectalis muscle and the transverse area of the anus levator muscle in athletes [9].

Furthermore, there still exist many investigations and speculations concerning the role of physical activity on the PFM. There exist two antagonistic hypotheses as to how exercise can affect the PFM. The first hypothesis is that physical activity is able to strengthen the pelvic floor muscle, while the second hypothesis is that physical activity may overload, stretch and weaken the PFM [10], where this second hypothesis may lead to urinary leakage.

In this sense, is important to understand the differences of the PFM between runners and sedentary, as there exist biomechanical modifications, cardiorespiratory and physiological problems encountered in those practicing running activities. In particular, in feminine athletes, it is important to analyze the effect of practicing this sport on the PFM, as the training of these muscles is a physiotherapeutic treatment used in women with UI [11]. In this context, the objective of this study was to compare the strength and endurance of the PFM in women that run and those that are sedentary. Muscle strength can be defined as the maximal force that a muscle can generate and is often referred to as the weight the muscle can lift once, or the one repetition maximum (1RM) [12]. Muscle Endurance is the ability of a

muscle group to sustain muscle contractions over a period of time [13]. The hypothesis is that the abdominal strength in women that run is greater than in sedentary women. Therefore, the strength and endurance on the PFM must also be greater for these women.

II. METHODS

This is an observational, cross-sectional study with a quantitative approach. The research study was realized at the Health Center of the University Complex of the Cerrado Patrocínio (UNICERP), in the city of Patrocínio/MG, during the period of September to December of 2017.

The research study was approved by the Scientific Initiation Committee for Research UNICERP. The volunteers signed the term of free prior informed consent (FPIC), with their full agreement to participate in the study after the objectives of the research study were clarified.

A. Study population

The study was performed with 51 women, divided into two groups: 27 women runners and 24 sedentary women. The runner group were women that run at least 10 km/week, the non-runner group was composed of sedentary women, where convenience sampling was used for sample homogeneity regarding age. Women who complied with the following requirements were included in the study: 18 years or more of age, no signs of/or self-declared symptoms of menopause. Excluded from the study were pregnant women, women who had given birth within the last four months, diabetics, women with a history of pelvic or abdominal surgery within the last year.

In order to obtain the socio-demographic data for the women, as well as the profile for the running and sedentary groups, a specific evaluation sheet was employed that contained information such as marital status, income, education and obstetric history.

B. PFM outcome assessment

To make the comparison between the PFM of the runner and sedentary groups of women, evaluations were made for strength and endurance. These were obtained by means of digital palpation, who tests the ability of the PFM to contract through touch and the vaginal cones respectively [13-14]. To avoid bias related to the experience of the evaluator and bias related to the evaluation of two different people, the evaluation of all volunteers was carried out by a single experienced physiotherapist.

C. Measurements: Strength

The evaluation of the strength of the PFM was performed by means of bidigital vaginal palpation by the same evaluator. To this end, the volunteers were invited to empty their bladders and lie down on an appropriate stretcher in the supine position, with hips and knees flexed and feet supported. To perform this procedure the evaluator used gloves and neutral gel. The evaluator introduced the index and middle fingers approximately 4 cm to 6 cm inside the vagina and positioned at 4 o'clock and 8 o'clock to monitor muscle activity. Moderate pressure was applied over the

muscle bulk to assist in the initiation of the appropriate muscle contraction. Following this, the volunteer was requested to perform a maximum contraction of the PFM for a strength evaluation. The volunteers followed the instruction for a movement “inward and forward” [15].

The grading of the PFM was performed in accordance with the validated Modified Oxford Scale, proposed by Laycock and Jerwood [10]. This scale possesses a grading that starts at zero (absence of muscle contraction) and possesses as a maximum limit 5 (examiner’s finger is raised against strong resistance). The scores for the strength evaluation of the pelvic floor, in accordance with the Oxford Scale, are shown on Table 1.

TABLE I - OXFORD SCALE FOR EVALUATING PELVIC FLOOR STRENGTH

Degree	Pelvic Floor behavior
0	Absence of contraction of the perineal muscles
1	Very slight unsustained muscle contraction
2	Presence of slight but sustained contraction
3	Contraction felt with increase of vaginal pressure that squeezes the examiner’s fingers with a slight elevation of the posterior vaginal wall
4	Satisfactory contraction that squeezes the examiner’s fingers toward the pubic symphysis
5	Strong contraction tight squeezing of the examiner’s fingers with positive movement toward the pubic symphysis

Source: (LAYCOCK; JERWOOD, 2001)^[10]

D. Measurements: Endurance

The evaluation for the endurance of the PFM was performed with vaginal cones (Quark trademark). The use of cones was intended as a measuring tool as well as a training method [1]. The cones are manufactured using the polymer ABS, all of equal size, with five different weight ratios (20g, 32g, 45g, 57g and 70g), with a nylon wire attached at the end to facilitate its extraction.

An evaluation was performed with the vaginal cones. The evaluation was initiated with the introduction into the vagina of the lightest cone, in the dorsal decubitus position, with the hip and knees flexed. The nylon wire was exposed and free to facilitate the removal of the cone. After the introduction of the cone, the patients were submitted to an increasing sequence of effort based on tasks that increase intra-abdominal pressure, adapted from Gameiro et al. [16], Fischer and Riolo [17]. and Krhut et al. [18], these consisted of:

- 1) Walk during one minute;
- 2) Climb up/down stairs during 30 seconds;
- 3) Jump (10 times);
- 4) Standing up from a sitting position (10 times);
- 5) Cough four times.

Each volunteer individually determined the intensity of these tasks. When the device remained in the vaginal canal, it was subsequently removed and the next cone of higher weight inserted, and so on in succession, until the weight was outside the endurance of the volunteer to hold it. The classification of PFM endurance was performed in function

of the maximum weight of the sustained cone at the completion of the tasks set. The value of the maximum sustained weights for obtaining endurance, were organized on a table for posterior statistical analyzes.

E. Statistical Analyses

Sample size was calculated using GPower 3.1.9.4, with significance set at 0.05 and power set at 0.9, the sample size should not be less than 44. In order to perform the statistical analysis of the data, the normality of each characteristic (strength and endurance) and the homogeneity between the ages of the runners and sedentary individuals for each group is successively verified by the Shapiro-Wilk test. If the normality of data is accepted, the comparison of the groups will be performed using the t student test for independent samples. Under the hypothesis that the normality of the data is rejected, the Mann-Whitney test will be used, while considering in both cases, $p < 0.05$. Statistical analysis was performed on the software R.

III. RESULTS

A total of 51 volunteers were included in the assessment. No volunteers were excluded from the study, as shown in Fig. 1 that shows the flow diagram of individuals at each stage of study. The hypothesis that the data originate from a normal distribution was not confirmed for any of the data (age, body mass index (BMI), endurance and strength). As such, the Mann-Whitney test was performed over all data. Table 2 presents the result for the statistical analysis performed for the ages of both groups. One notes from the p-value column that there was no statistical difference between the ages of the groups studied.

Fig 1 - Flow diagram of individuals at each stage of study

TABLE II - DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

Characteristics	Group Runners	Group Sedentary	p-value
Age (years)	39.6±9.6	34±12.4	.1
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.8±3.7	24.7±3.6	.9

Values are mean ±SD (Standard Deviation)

One notes that the running women possess higher scores for strength of the PFM during the proposed tasks, thus demonstrating a significant difference between the two groups, as shown on Table 3. Noteworthy from the evaluation with the vaginal cones, the group composed of women

runners presented a higher average, as can be seen on Table 3. However, there was no statistical difference found between the two groups when it came to evaluating endurance using vaginal cones, as shown by the value of p .

TABLE III - PELVIC FLOOR MUSCLE STRENGTH (MODIFIED OXFORD SCALE) AND PELVIC FLOOR MUSCLE ENDURANCE (VAGINAL CONES WEIGHT METHOD)

Characteristics	Group Runners	Group Sedentary	p-value
Strength	3.6±1.0	2.7±0.8	<0.001
Endurance	48.0±20.7	43.5±19.5	0.36

Values are mean ± SD

The dispersion graph and the Boxplot are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 – Dispersion graph and Boxplot. A – Dispersion of strength (index of the Modified Oxford scale): Asterisk – Running women, Circle – Sedentary women, B – Boxplot of strength (index for the Modified Oxford Scale), C – Dispersion of endurance (weight of sustained cones): Asterisk – Running women, Circle – Sedentary women, D – Boxplot of endurance (weight of sustained cones).

As can be seen from Fig. 2A, the scores for the women runners (Asterisk) in general are higher than those of the sedentary women (Circle), and which have a higher concentration on the upper part of the graph, and as such justify the statistical difference. However, in Fig. 2C, the difference between the weights of the cones cannot be seen between the groups, as there is no positioning standard on the scatter plot.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the pelvic floor, comparing runners and sedentary women to explore the effects of physical activity on the pelvic floor muscles. In this manner, by comparing the strength and endurance of the PFM in runners and sedentary women, it was proven through statistical tests (Mann-Whitney), that there was a significant difference of strength of the PFM between women that were runners and those that were sedentary. This difference can be explained by Bø [6], who states that the impact and increase of abdominal pressure, which should be neutralized by the PFM in athletes performing high impact activities, is much greater than in the general population. Therefore, the pelvic floor needs to be much stronger in elite athletes.

The statements put forward by Bø [6] are reinforced by Leitner et al [19] and Borin et al [20], which state that during running exercises the forces reacting vertically with the soil can increase significantly, hence the PFM of athletes need to be stronger as a means of mitigating these forces.

The increase in strength of the PFM, can still be explained by the study from Sapsford and Hodges [21], where they state that an involuntary muscular activation associated with a voluntary contraction of the abdominal muscles, denominated as co-activation, was seen in individuals in an upright position. This is due to the fact that in an upright position there is an increase in hydrostatic forces of the abdomen and pelvic floor, resulting from the force of gravity. Placing emphasis to the claim made by Sapsford and Hodges [21]. Almeida et al [22] who state that the more frequent the impact associated with the increase in intra-abdominal pressure, greater is the need for containment and support of the pelvic organs by the PFM, which should themselves be trained in order to preserve their function.

The findings of the present study support the hypothesis that the strength of the PFM is related to the practice of high impact physical exercise. Despite the result found in the present study, Bø and Sundgot-Borgen [23] concluded that female elite athletes had a high prevalence of stress and urge incontinence.

The apparent conflict between the results of this study and those from Bø and Sundgot-Borgen [23], can be explained according to Ree et al [9] where they state that there exist two opposing hypotheses concerning how exercises can affect the pelvic floor. The first hypothesis is based on the fact that physical exercise increases abdominal pressure, thus acting as a training stimulus. The second hypothesis is based on the fact if the increase in abdominal pressure is not counterbalanced by an equal contraction of the pelvic floor muscles, they can become overloaded, stretched and weakened over the long term. In this study, it was shown that the PFM of runners are stronger and more resistant than in the PFM of sedentary individuals.

However, it cannot be stated that there was a validation of the first hypothesis, as it is not known until which point the strengthening of the PFM in runners is sufficient for counterbalancing the increase in abdominal pressure. Therefore, there still exists the need for more studies on the subject. These data reinforce the importance of trainers and professionals, involved in the improvement of performance of athletes, to observe muscular exercises related to the PFM, as these exercises can act in both the prevention and treatment of UI [6].

The difference found in strength of the PFM is possibly linked to the anatomical and functional differences between runners and sedentary individuals, due to the practical application of running. In the study by Kruger et al [4], the objective was to characterize the muscular function of the pelvic floor in a population of nulliparous athletes, which trained frequently and intensely with high impact exercises. These were then compared to non-athletes, using bi/tri dimensional pelvic floor images, thus showing that there exist various anatomical and functional differences in the PFM.

The endurance of PFM did not present any significant difference between women runners and sedentary women. This fact can be explained by Bø [24], where the author performed a study on the strength measurement capacity of PFM, using vaginal cones. The conclusion reached was that there exists a low correlation between the strength of the PFM measured by digital palpitation and the ability of incontinent women to secure the cones.

This study presented some limitations. Firstly, Goldstick and Constantini [25] state that athletes report urine loss at the end of training sessions or in the second stage of competitions, which suggests that the endurance of the PFM is demanded in these stages. Therefore, in order that the effect of such comparisons becomes more effective, it will be necessary to perform more strenuous tasks on the women (runners and sedentary). However, the tasks that were performed in the study protocol did not meet this need. Second, for future studies, the investigation into the balance between intra-abdominal and intra-urethral pressure, besides strength and endurance will be of vital importance. In addition, there exists the need to assess the strength and endurance of the PFM in those athletes who have UI, preferably before and after the sport practice (running), in order to better explore the hypothesis presented herein.

In conclusion, the study proposed herein, based on the Modified Oxford Scale and the cone technique, confirms there is a difference of strength in the PFM between runners and sedentary individuals, where women that run presented higher strength of the PFM than sedentary women. However, the endurance of the PFM did not present any significant difference between women runners and sedentary women. The conclusions drawn from the results obtained in this study are in agreement with those supported in the literature, as they show that strength of the PFM is different between runners and sedentary women, where strength is reportedly higher in runners.

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